

A Lagrangian differencing dynamics method for granular flow modeling

Chong Peng^a, Martina Bašić^b, Branko Blagojević^b, Josip Bašić^b, Wei Wu^{a,*}

^a Institut für Geotechnik, Universität für Bodenkultur, 1180 Vienna, Austria

^b Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering and Naval Architecture, University of Split, 21000 Split, Croatia

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Lagrangian differencing dynamics
Meshless method
Non-Newtonian flow
Drucker-Prager yield criterion
Granular flow
Granular impact on structures

ABSTRACT

In this paper, a new Lagrangian differencing dynamics (LDD) method is presented for the simulation of granular flows. LDD is a truly meshless method, which employs second-order consistent spatial operators derived from the Taylor expansion and point renormalization. A decoupled pressure-velocity formulation is employed to derive the pressure Poisson equation, which ensures smooth pressure results in time. Granular media are modeled as viscoplastic materials with the Drucker-Prager yield surface. The velocity equation is formulated and solved in an implicit form, in order to handle large viscosities from the constitutive model. Furthermore, a position-based dynamics technique is used to maintain uniform distribution of the Lagrangian points. The presented LDD method for granular flows is validated by simulating two numerical examples. The results are compared with experimental and numerical data from the literature.

1. Introduction

Modeling of dry granular flows and fast landslides using continuum-based methods has seen rapid progress in recent years, mainly owing to the advancement in computational methods and constitutive models. In particular, various Lagrangian particle- and point-based methods are widely employed in modeling granular materials, e.g., smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) (Bui et al., 2008; Chambon et al., 2011; Peng et al., 2016), material point method (MPM) (Mast, 2013; Xu et al., 2019), and particle finite element method (PFEM) (Becker and Idelsohn, 2016; Larsson et al., 2020). The main reason of their popularity is that problems involving granular materials often have large deformations and complex free-surfaces, which are inconvenient to handle using traditional mesh-based methods, because additional numerical techniques are required to capture the moving interfaces (Staron et al., 2013; Salazar et al., 2016). Applications of point-based methods in granular material modeling include granular flows (Szewc, 2017; Yang et al., 2020), interaction with structures (Zhan et al., 2019b, 2020; Ng et al., 2020), landslides and debris flows (Pastor et al., 2009; Dai et al., 2014), among others. Furthermore, various constitutive models are employed in previous studies, from classical models from soil mechanics, e.g., the Drucker-Prager model (Bui et al., 2008), the Mohr-Coulomb model (Zhao et al., 2019), the hypoplastic models (Peng et al., 2015, 2016), the

Matsuoka–Nakai model (Mast, 2013), to rheological models such as the Bingham model (Li et al., 2020), the viscoplastic Drucker-Prager model (Dai et al., 2014; Szewc, 2017), and the $\mu(I)$ model (Chambon et al., 2011), where granular materials are treated as non-Newtonian incompressible fluids.

Recently, a novel Lagrangian meshless method, the Lagrangian differencing dynamics (LDD)¹ was proposed to simulate incompressible fluid flows (Bašić et al., 2018, 2020). Similar to SPH, LDD is a truly meshless method, in which the computational domain is represented by a point cloud; therefore, no topological information is needed. Unlike SPH and other meshless methods, LDD employs different techniques to perform the meshless interpolation and to solve the governing equations. In the LDD method, the Taylor expansion is combined with a renormalization scheme (Lanson and Vila, 2008) to construct the discrete gradient and Laplacian operators with second order consistency (Bašić et al., 2018). Different from many normalized or corrected SPH methods (Chen et al., 1999; Liu et al., 2017), the discrete gradient operator in the LDD method does not use the spatial derivatives of the kernel function. In this sense, its approximation of gradient is similar to the so-called kernel-gradient-free SPH (KGF-SPH) (Huang et al., 2019). However, in LDD it is not needed to solve the value of the field function, so only one inversion of the $d \times d$ renormalization matrix per point is required instead of the $(d+1) \times (d+1)$ matrix in KGF-SPH, where d is

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: wei.wu@boku.ac.at (W. Wu).

¹ The method was originally named as Lagrangian finite-difference method in Bašić et al. (2020). However, in private communications, the authors of the original paper suggested the new name because they believe the original name cannot describe the features of the method.

the number of dimensions. Moreover, compared with meshless methods that are derived based on the moving least-squares (MLS) approximation, such as the finite point-set method (Tiwari and Kuhnert, 2003; Drumm et al., 2008) and the finite point method (Oñate et al., 2001), the LDD method has the same second-order accuracy but needs lower computational cost. This is because at each point the finite point-set method and the finite point method need to solve a small linear system, whose dimension is larger than the number of neighboring points. On the other hand, LDD only needs to calculate the inversion of a $d \times d$ matrix. This efficiency makes it suitable for complex transient problems.

More importantly, previously introduced meshless approximations of the Laplacian operator often employ nested summations, directly use the second-order kernel derivatives, or combine kernel approximations with finite differences (Morris et al., 1997). However, these methods may be less accurate, and more sensitive to the point distribution (Basa et al., 2009; Bašić et al., 2018). On the other hand, the LDD method achieves the accurate approximation of the Laplacian operator without using the first- and second-order kernel derivatives. Furthermore, it is second-order accurate when employed to solve Poisson equations (Bašić et al., 2018). Because of its accuracy in approximating the gradient and Laplacian operators, it is a promising method for problems involving dynamic free-surface flows.

Consequently, LDD can be employed to model granular flows using rheological models. Owing to the solution of the Poisson pressure equation (PPE), it should generate smooth pressure results and avoid the numerical noise observed in weakly-compressible SPH (Szewc, 2017). However, the original LDD with explicit velocity solver (Bašić et al., 2020) cannot be directly used. This is because the rheological models used to simulate granular materials tend to generate very high viscosity in slow motion areas. If the momentum equation is solved explicitly like the original LDD (Bašić et al., 2020), numerical instability will be observed. To avoid this numerical instability, we need to either use very small time step (Zago et al., 2018) or formulate an implicit velocity solver for LDD.

In this work, the LDD method is employed to model granular flows, in which the materials are modeled as incompressible viscoplastic media that obey the Drucker-Prager (DP) yield criterion. The system is simulated using the non-Newtonian Navier-Stokes equations. The pressure field is obtained from solving the Poisson pressure equation (PPE) derived from the incompressible (divergence-free) condition. An implicit velocity solver is introduced to compute the velocity field, which can handle high viscosities from the viscoplastic DP model and achieve stable solutions with large time steps. Furthermore, the position-based dynamics (PBD) technique (Macklin and Müller, 2013) is used to regularize the point positions, which ensures the volume conservation and regular point distribution. The developed method is first validated by simulating the collapse of a granular column, then it is applied to model the impact of granular flows on a rigid barrier. Finally, the performance of the LDD method in reproducing flow dynamics and impact forces are analyzed.

2. Governing equations

In continuum-based modeling of granular flows, it is common practice to consider granular materials as incompressible or weakly-compressible fluids that follow different yield conditions (Chambon et al., 2011; Dai et al., 2014; Hu et al., 2015; Li et al., 2020). Therefore, the governing equations of the system are the generalized Navier-Stokes equations, which can be written in the following Lagrangian form

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + \frac{\eta}{\rho} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{g} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the velocity vector, ρ is the bulk density of the granular

material, p is the pressure, η is the dynamic viscosity, \mathbf{g} denotes the gravitational acceleration vector, D/Dt is the material derivative, ∇ and ∇^2 are the gradient and Laplacian operators, respectively. Eq. (1) is the divergence-free condition, which comes from the incompressible constraint, while Eq. (2) is the momentum conservation equation.

Granular matters can behave like a solid, a liquid, or a gas (Jaeger et al., 1996). As a result, the motions of granular material have three regimes, i.e. quasi-static, dense, and gaseous. In the quasi-static regime, the motion occurs slowly and grains have long-term frictional contact with their neighbors. On the other hand, in the gaseous regime the grains move freely, only occasionally collide with other grains (Campbell, 1990). The motions between the quasi-static and the gaseous regimes are termed as dense granular flow (Jop et al., 2006). During the transition between the quasi-static and dense flow regimes, the dilatancy that is unique to granular materials plays an important role, because it controls the change of volume and shear strength, which is critical to problems such as slope stability and initiation of failure (Manzari and Nour, 2000). However, when the granular material experiences large deformation and starts to flow, it should reach the critical state where the volume keeps unchanged and the dilatancy becomes zero if the pressure is fixed (Schofield and Wroth, 1968). The compressibility of granular materials under the critical state is dependent on the bulk stiffness, which is usually very large such that the speed of mechanical wave is much larger than the material velocity. This observation justifies the employment of the incompressible constraint Eq. (1). The irrelevance of dilatancy in granular flows is also confirmed by previous studies on the collapse of granular columns (Neto and Borja, 2018). Consequently, the most important material feature in granular flows is the pressure-dependency, i.e., the yield strength is dependent on the effective normal stress.

In this study, a viscoplastic model with the Drucker-Prager (DP) yield condition is used to model granular media. It has simple formulation yet is able to capture the salient behaviors of granular media. Therefore, it is a common choice for numerical modeling of granular flows and fast landslides (Dai et al., 2014; Becker and Idelsohn, 2016; Salazar et al., 2016; Szewc, 2017; Dai et al., 2017). The model is expressed as

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\gamma} = 0, & \text{if } \tau < p \tan \phi \\ \tau = (p \tan \phi) \frac{\dot{\gamma}}{\dot{\gamma}}, & \text{if } \tau \geq p \tan \phi \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\dot{\gamma} = \nabla \mathbf{u} + (\nabla \mathbf{u})^T$ is the strain-rate tensor, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the deviatoric stress tensor, ϕ is the friction angle. $\dot{\gamma}$ and τ denote the scalar measurements of the strain-rate and deviatoric stress tensors, which are defined as $\dot{\gamma} = \sqrt{\dot{\gamma} : \dot{\gamma} / 2}$ and $\tau = \sqrt{\boldsymbol{\tau} : \boldsymbol{\tau} / 2}$, respectively. The viscoplastic DP model described in Eq. (3) states that if the stress state is within the yield surface, the material remains underformed, which means it is either static or undergoes rigid body motion. Once the stress reaches the yield surface, the material starts to flow. In the flow regime, the stress tensor and the strain rate tensor are assumed to be coaxial (He et al., 2018a,b).

On the other hand, from fluid mechanics point of view, the shear stress tensor can be computed by multiplying the viscosity with the strain rate tensor

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \eta \dot{\gamma} \quad (4)$$

Substituting the above equation into Eq. (3), the dynamic viscosity is obtained as

$$\eta = \frac{p \tan \phi}{\dot{\gamma}} \quad (5)$$

Note that in the viscoplastic DP model the viscosity inside the yield surface is undefined. From a numerical point of view, this means that the viscosity becomes infinite in regions with zero strain rate, thus inducing difficulties in numerical simulations. To avoid this singularity, the regularization method proposed in Papanastasiou (1987) is employed

$$\eta = \frac{\rho \tan \phi}{\dot{\gamma}} (1 - e^{-m\dot{\gamma}}) \quad (6)$$

where m is a regularization parameter. It can be seen that in the solid-like regions, where $\dot{\gamma}$ approaches zero, the viscosity becomes $m\rho \tan \phi$. Note that Eq. (6) is still singular when $\dot{\gamma}$ is zero, which causes numerical instability. So in our implementation, after the viscosity is obtained, we check whether the resulted μ is a valid number. If it is not a number (NaN), then the limit $m\rho \tan \phi$ is used instead.

In order to mimic the solid-like behavior in the static regions, very large values for the viscosity should be used. Therefore, the regularization parameter m should be large enough to correctly reproduce the physics. The influence of m was discussed in several studies (Salazar et al., 2016; Becker and Idelsohn, 2016; Peng et al., 2021). Generally, a bigger m provides a better approximation of the original model Eq. (5), but gives rise to a larger condition number of the linear system resulted from the implicit velocity solver (Becker and Idelsohn, 2016), which will be introduced in Section 3.2. So the selection of m is a trade-off between accuracy and conditioning of the system (Becker and Idelsohn, 2016). In practice, m is chosen to be as small as possible, but large enough to reproduce correct flow physics (Peng et al., 2021). The influence of m will be studied in Section 4.1.1.

3. Lagrangian differencing dynamics for granular materials

Lagrangian differencing dynamics (LDD) is introduced to solve the generalized Navier-Stokes equations. The developed method has the following features. First, it employs the second-order consistent approximations for the gradient and Laplacian operators. Second, smooth and accurate pressure results are obtained through solving the Poisson pressure equations (PPE) derived from the incompressible restriction. Third, the viscous effect is considered with an implicit velocity solver, so the solid-like areas with extremely large viscosities can be modelled without compromising the numerical efficiency and stability. Fourth, a point regularization scheme is employed, which gives rise to regular point distribution and accurate computation. In this section, the formulations of LDD are introduced, the implementation of the numerical method is detailed.

3.1. LDD approximations

LDD is a truly meshless method, in which the modeled materials are discretized by a set of points without any connectivity information. The points carry physical information, e.g., position, velocity, pressure, and viscosity, and move with the material velocity. It should be pointed out that in LDD the points only serve as interpolation points. So unlike SPH particles, the points do not have mass or volume. Similar to other meshless methods, a compactly supported weighting function is employed to compute the interaction between points. The weighting

function, $W(r, R)$, should be continuous, smooth, and symmetric, where r is the distance between two points. R is the smoothing radius, which means the kernel function is zero if $r \geq R$. A spiky kernel (Shakibaenia and Jin, 2010) is used in this work with $R = 2.5\Delta r$, where Δr is the average point spacing. The kernel function writes

$$W(r, R) = \left(1 - \frac{r}{R}\right)^3 \quad 0 \leq r \leq R \quad (7)$$

Different from SPH, in LDD, only the immediately neighbouring points are considered in the approximation, while the accuracy is guaranteed owing to a renormalization scheme, which will be introduced subsequently. We define a truncation radius r_0 , which has $r_0 < R$. The points are excluded from the computation if their distances from the centering point are larger than r_0 . Note that the truncation radius does not change the form of the kernel function, which is still based on the smoothing radius R . A further comparison between LDD and SPH is shown in Fig. 1. In SPH the radius of the kernel function and the truncation radius are usually identical, taken as $2h$ (Peng et al., 2019b; Crespo et al., 2015; Zhan et al., 2019a). On the other hand, in LDD these two radii are different, and we have $r_0 < R$.

Meshless approximations with truncated support domains can also be found in a few SPH simulations, where only the immediately neighbouring particles are considered (Islam and Peng, 2019; Islam and Shaw, 2020). This truncation can improve the efficiency, keep the local feature of the field function, and avoid excessive diffusion in the approximation of the spatial operators (Bašić et al., 2018). In this study, the truncation radius is taken as $r_0 = 1.5\Delta r$. This is a roughly estimated size used to ensure that all the immediately neighboring particles are included in the computation. Consequently, the LDD method is more efficient in the function approximation when compared with SPH, which often uses support domains size ($2h$) ranging between $2.4\Delta r$ and $3.3\Delta r$ (Bui et al., 2008; Crespo et al., 2015; Peng et al., 2019b). SPH employs relatively large $2h/\Delta r$ ratio to ensure the accuracy, because the convergence requirements of SPH approximation are $\Delta r \rightarrow 0$ and $h/\Delta r \rightarrow \infty$ (Zhu et al., 2015; Peng et al., 2019b).

Note that it is not recommended having $R = r_0 = 1.5\Delta r$. This is because that the Spiky kernel decreases very fast with increasing distance r (Shakibaenia and Jin, 2010). If $R = 1.5\Delta r$ is used, $W(\Delta r, R)$, which is a typical kernel function value for the immediately neighboring particles, would be too small.

3.1.1. Function approximation

The meshless function approximation is to calculate the function value $f(\mathbf{x})$ at an arbitrary location \mathbf{x} using the function values $f(\mathbf{x}_j)$, where \mathbf{x}_j indicates a point in the discrete point set Ω . To achieve this, we first consider how to partition the differential volume dV at \mathbf{x} . Following Hopkins (2015), the differential volume dV can be distributed fractionally among the surrounding points using a weighting function. Therefore, each point in the neighbourhood of \mathbf{x} can obtain a fraction of

Fig. 1. Sketch of support domains in LDD and SPH.

the differential volume. For example, the fraction associated with point \mathbf{x}_j can be written as

$$\psi_j(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{\omega(\mathbf{x})} W(r_j, R) \quad (8)$$

where $r_j = \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_j\|$ is the distance between \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}_j . The term $\omega(\mathbf{x})$ is used to ensure that the summation of all fractions associated with the surrounding points is equal to unity. Its form is written as

$$\omega(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_j W(r_j, R) \quad (9)$$

In a similar way, the function value $f(\mathbf{x})$ can be computed by summing up all the fractions associated with the surrounding points

$$\langle f(\mathbf{x}) \rangle_i = \sum_j \psi_j(\mathbf{x}) f(\mathbf{x}_j) \quad (10)$$

Owing to the normalization, the above approximation converges to the exact value if the spatial resolution approaches zero. It has zeroth-order consistency even with truncated support domains and highly irregular point arrangements.

3.1.2. Gradient approximation

The accurate approximation of spatial derivatives of field functions is crucial in numerical simulations. In LDD, the Taylor expansion is combined with a meshless weighted summation to construct the gradient approximation. Following Lanson and Vila (2008), Bašić et al. (2018), the approximated gradient at \mathbf{x}_i can be written as

$$\langle \nabla f \rangle_i = \sum_j W_{ij} \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{x}_{ij} (f_j - f_i) \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i$ is the vector between the two points i and j , $W_{ij} = W(r_{ij}, h)$ is the kernel function with $r_{ij} = \|\mathbf{x}_{ij}\|$, f_i and f_j are the function values at \mathbf{x}_i and \mathbf{x}_j , respectively. The renormalization matrix \mathbf{B}_i is defined as

$$\mathbf{B}_i = \left(\sum_j W_{ij} \mathbf{x}_{ij} \otimes \mathbf{x}_{ij} \right)^{-1} \quad (12)$$

where \otimes is the outer product between two vectors. The detailed derivation of the renormalization matrix and the gradient approximation can be found in Bašić et al. (2018). Note that the approximation of the gradient does not need the spatial derivatives of the kernel function. This is different from the corrective SPH (Randles and Libersky, 1996; Chen et al., 1999) or the kernel gradient correction SPH (Liu et al., 2017). The gradient approximation in LDD proves to be second-order consistent, and performs well on highly irregular point arrangements (Lanson and Vila, 2008; Bašić et al., 2018).

3.1.3. Laplacian approximation

In the modeling of granular flows, both the Poisson pressure equation and the viscous term contain the Laplacian operator. In meshless methods, many approaches were proposed to approximate the second-order derivatives. For instance, in the finite point-set method (Tiwari and Kuhnert, 2003) and the finite point method (Oñate et al., 2001), the second-order derivatives are obtained together with the first-order derivatives by solving a linear system resulted from the weighted least-square (WLS) or MLS approximations. The approximations of the second-order derivatives in these two methods are second-order consistent; however, they need to solve a relatively large linear system per point, whose dimension is larger than the number of points in the support domain. As a result, they have high computational cost and are less efficient in modeling transient problems. There are also many

methods in SPH to approximate the Laplacian operator, e.g., the nested summation, the direct employment of second-order derivatives of the kernel function, and the combination of SPH approximation and finite difference. Fatehi and Manzari (2011) analyzed the commonly-used methods for the approximation of second-order derivatives in SPH, and found that all of them suffer from low accuracy and in the best case are zeroth-order consistent.

Bašić et al. (2018) proposed three types of Laplacian approximations based on Eq. (11) and the Taylor expansion. In LDD, the sum version of the three approximation methods is employed, which has the following form

$$\langle \nabla^2 f \rangle_i = 2d \frac{\sum_j W_{ij} (f_j - f_i) (1 - \mathbf{x}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{o}_i)}{\sum_j W_{ij} r_{ij}^2 (1 - \mathbf{x}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{o}_i)} \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{o}_i is an offset vector that describes the local point arrangement

$$\mathbf{o}_i = \sum_j W_{ij} \mathbf{x}_{ij} \quad (14)$$

It is theoretically proved and numerically validated that the above Laplacian approximation has the second-order accuracy when employed in solving Poisson equations (Bašić et al., 2018). It does not need the first or second order derivatives of the kernel function. The computation is also efficient as the renormalization matrix \mathbf{B}_i and the offset vector \mathbf{o}_i can be precomputed at the beginning of each step.

3.2. Pressure and velocity solvers

The unknowns in the system Eqs. (1) and (2) are the pressure and velocity fields. Usually, the pressure and velocity can be solved in a decoupled manner, using the projection scheme (Chorin, 1968; Cummins and Rudman, 1999; Peng et al., 2019a) or the velocity-pressure formulation (Johnston and Liu, 2004; Bašić et al., 2020). In LDD, the original incompressible condition is replaced by the following pressure Poisson equation (PPE) (Bašić et al., 2020)

$$\nabla^2 p = \rho \nabla \cdot \left(\mathbf{g} - \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} \right) \quad (15)$$

In granular flow problems, the body force \mathbf{g} is always constant, so it has $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{g} = 0$. The divergence of the acceleration can be written as

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} \right) = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} \right) + (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u})^2 + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \quad (16)$$

As the spatial and temporal derivative operators are commutative, it holds $\nabla \cdot (\partial \mathbf{u} / \partial t) = \partial (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) / \partial t$. According to the incompressible condition, in theoretical and continuous sense, all the three terms on the right hand side (RHS) of Eq. (16) are zero. In numerical simulations, however, the velocity divergence is not exactly zero because of errors from numerical approximation, truncation, initial conditions and other sources. As the second and third terms on the RHS of Eq. (16) are much smaller than the first term if $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \neq 0$, only the first term is retained in the PPE. Consequently, Eq. (15) can be simplified as

$$\nabla^2 p = -\rho \frac{\partial (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} \quad (17)$$

With the LDD Laplacian operator defined in Eq. (13), the above PPE at a point i can be discretized as

$$2d \frac{\sum_j W_{ij} (p_j - p_i) (1 - \mathbf{x}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{o}_i)}{\sum_j W_{ij} r_{ij}^2 (1 - \mathbf{x}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{o}_i)} = b_i \quad (18)$$

where b_i is the discrete form of the RHS of Eq. (17), defined as

$$b_i = -\rho\lambda_{F,i}\langle\nabla\cdot\mathbf{u}\rangle_i, \quad \langle\nabla\cdot\mathbf{u}\rangle_i = \sum_j W_{ij}\mathbf{B}_i\mathbf{x}_{ij}\cdot(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \quad (19)$$

where $\lambda_{F,i} = c_i/\Delta t$ is a divergence damping coefficient. According to Eq. (17), it holds $\lambda_F = 1/\Delta t$ with Δt being the time step. However, it was found that this choice often leads to temporal oscillations in the pressure field (Cheng et al., 2018). Following Bašić et al. (2020), in this study $\lambda_{F,i} = c_i/\Delta t$ is employed, where c_i is the maximum difference of the velocities of points in the support domain of i . This treatment results in smooth pressure variation in time. The PPEs from all points in the computational domain form a linear system, which is solved using the bi-conjugate gradient stabilized method (BiCGSTAB) in a matrix-free manner.

After obtaining the pressure field by solving the PPE, the pressure gradient $\langle\nabla p\rangle_i$ can be readily computed using Eq. (11). Similarly, the strain rate tensor $\dot{\gamma} = \nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T$ can be computed through the discretization of the velocity gradient

$$\langle\nabla\mathbf{u}\rangle_i = \sum_j W_{ij}\mathbf{B}_i\mathbf{x}_{ij} \otimes (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \quad (20)$$

With the strain rate tensor and pressure, the viscosity can be obtained using the viscoplastic DP model Eq. (6). Therefore, the momentum Eq. (2) can be solved explicitly by the direct discretization of the viscous term using the discrete Laplacian operator. However, such an approach has many drawbacks. Usually, in the solid-like regions, the viscosities obtained from the viscoplastic DP model have very large values. If an explicit time integration method is employed to solve the momentum equation, very small time steps should be used (Zago et al., 2018). Hence, the following implicit velocity solver is introduced to improve the efficiency and stability of the LDD method.

Similar to the explicit method described above, in the implicit method, the viscosity at each point is first computed based on the constitutive model. In the second step, the momentum equation is rearranged and written in the following discrete form

$$\frac{\mathbf{u}_i^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}_i^n}{\Delta t} - \frac{2d}{\rho} \frac{\sum_j \bar{\eta}_{ij} W_{ij} (1 - \mathbf{x}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{o}_i) (\mathbf{u}_j^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}_i^{n+1})}{\sum_j W_{ij} r_{ij} (1 - \mathbf{x}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{o}_i)} = -\frac{\langle\nabla p\rangle_i}{\rho} + \mathbf{g} \quad (21)$$

where $\bar{\eta}_{ij} = (\eta_i + \eta_j)/2$ is the average dynamic viscosity, n and $n+1$ are the current and the next computational steps. In the above equation, all the quantities are known except \mathbf{u}^{n+1} . A linear system can be obtained by combining the momentum equations at all points. The velocities are then solved using a matrix-free Jacobi solver. With the implicit velocity solver, flows with extremely large viscosities can be easily modelled.

3.3. Advection and volume conservation

LDD is a Lagrangian method, in which the points are moved with the material velocity. Once the velocity is obtained using the implicit velocity solver, the points are advected using the following backward Euler time integration

$$\mathbf{x}_i^{n+1} = \mathbf{x}_i^n + \Delta t [1.5\mathbf{u}_i^{n+1} - 0.5\mathbf{u}_i^n] \quad (22)$$

Due to the high accuracy of the LDD approximation, the points follow closely the trajectories of streamlines. This often leads to anisotropic point distributions that result in larger approximation errors and the violation of volume conservation. This phenomenon is also observed in incompressible SPH (ISPH) and the moving particle semi-implicit method (MPS) if higher-order approximations are employed (Khayyer et al., 2017; Khayyer et al., 2019). ISPH and MPS usually employ the particle shifting (PS) technique (Xu et al., 2009; Khayyer et al., 2017; Khayyer et al., 2019) to restore regular point distribution. This is

achieved by slightly shifting points after the Lagrangian advection to maintain a uniform arrangement.

In this work, an alternative technique, the position-based dynamics (PBD) (Macklin and Müller, 2013), is employed to ensure the volume conservation and regular point distribution. In PBD, the points are slightly shifted iteratively by solving the following non-linear constraints

$$C_i = \frac{\rho_i}{\rho_{init}} - 1 \quad (23)$$

where ρ_i and ρ_{init} are the densities estimated from the current and the initial point distributions. The concept is to iteratively search for a slight shifting $\Delta\mathbf{x}_i$ of the position \mathbf{x}_i , which is obtained from the Lagrangian advection. The aim of this slight shifting is to ensure $C(\mathbf{x}_i + \Delta\mathbf{x}_i) = 0$. Note that the shifting is only applied to the internal points, the positions of the free-surface and boundary points are kept unchanged. The details of the derivation and implementation of PBD can be found in Macklin and Müller (2013). Compared with the PS technique, the PBD method does not need parameter tuning, and does not have any restrictions on the time step.

3.4. Boundary condition

In numerical modeling of granular flows, the free-surface boundary and the non-slip condition at the walls should be enforced. For the free-surface boundary, first a surface detection algorithm (Bašić et al., 2019) is employed to identify points on the free-surface. The identification is based on a non-dimensional number defined as

$$\xi = \sum_j (1 - \mathbf{x}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{B}_i \mathbf{o}_i) \quad (24)$$

Due to the missing neighbors, the points located on the free-surface has a ξ value close to zero. Bašić et al. (2019) employs a criterion of $\xi < 3$ for the identification of free-surface points, which is also adopted in this study. Once the free-surface is found, the Dirichlet boundary condition $p_i = b_i = 0$ is imposed when solving the PPE.

In LDD, the solid walls are represented by line segments. Boundary points are generated dynamically at the beginning of each step by projecting fluid points onto line segments, as shown in Fig. 2(a). The way to project the fluid points is shown in Fig. 2(b). There is a fluid point \mathbf{x} and a boundary segment AB, and the projection \mathbf{x}_p needs to be identified. Firstly, we define two vectors $\mathbf{r}_{Ax} = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_A$ and $\mathbf{r}_{AB} = \mathbf{x}_B - \mathbf{x}_A$, where \mathbf{x}_A and \mathbf{x}_B are the position vectors of the points A and B, respectively. Then a scalar value e is defined as

$$e = \frac{\mathbf{r}_{Ax} \cdot \mathbf{r}_{AB}}{\mathbf{r}_{AB} \cdot \mathbf{r}_{AB}} \quad (25)$$

If $0 \leq e \leq 1$ holds, then the projection is in the segment AB, and the position of the projection is

$$\mathbf{x}_p = \mathbf{x}_A + e\mathbf{r}_{AB} \quad (26)$$

Note that a loop over all possible segment is required to generate boundary points.

Because the fluid point distribution is uniform owing to the use of the PBD technique, the generated boundary points also have a high degree of regularity. At the boundary points, the Dirichlet boundary condition is $\mathbf{u}_i = \bar{\mathbf{u}}_i$, where $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_i$ is the prescribed boundary velocity. By doing so, the non-slip boundary condition is enforced.

3.5. Implementation and parallelization

The presented LDD method for granular flow modeling is imple-

Fig. 2. Dynamic generation of boundary points: (a) the generated boundary points, (b) the way to project a fluid point onto a boundary segment.

mented in an in-house solver named *Rhoxyz* (Bašić, 2019), which employs GPU parallelization to improve the numerical efficiency. The full computational process in one step is listed in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1. The computational process in one step.

1. Advect the fluid points and perform the PBD computation to regularize the point distribution
2. Remove all the boundary points, generate new boundary points based on new fluid positions
3. Pre-compute the renormalization matrix \mathbf{B}_i and the offset vector \mathbf{o}_i for each fluid point
4. Solve the PPE using the BiCGSTAB method
5. Compute the viscosity based on the viscoplastic MC model at each fluid point
6. Solve the velocity implicitly using the Jacobi method
7. Compute the velocity gradient and strain rate tensor at each fluid point.

4. Numerical examples

4.1. Collapse of a column of aluminum bars

A laboratory test on the collapse of a column consisting of aluminum bars was carried out by Bui et al. (2008), in which the bars are used to mimic granular materials to realize the true plane strain condition. Consequently, hereafter we simply refer the aluminum bars as granular material without further clarification. This laboratory test later became a popular benchmark for the numerical methods used for granular modeling. This is probably because of its simple geometry, clear physical process, and comprehensive description of the parameter calibration and test results. The test was simulated using SPH (Bui et al., 2008), MPM (Sołowski and Sloan, 2015), and PFEM (Becker and Idelsohn, 2016; Zhang et al., 2021). As shown in Fig. 3, in the test, a rectangular body of granular material is confined in a tank by a gate. The collapse of the granular body is triggered by quickly removing the gate. Driven by gravity, the granular material flows until a slope-shaped deposit is formed.

4.1.1. The flow process and final profile

In this work, the presented LDD method is employed to model the collapse of the granular column to check the performance of the method. The material parameters are taken from Bui et al. (2008): density $\rho =$

Fig. 3. Sketch of the granular collapse problem.

2650 kg/m^3 , friction angle $\phi = 19.8^\circ$. Initially, a simulation with point spacing $\Delta r = 2 \text{ mm}$ and the regularization parameter $m = 100 \text{ s}$ is performed. The influence of particle spacing and regularization parameter will be discussed subsequently. Fig. 4 shows the collapse process obtained from the initial simulation. It is found that the collapse happens above a failure surface, below which the material is at rest. With the development of the collapse, the failure surface gradually moves left until a final steady state is reached. In the final deposit, a small part of the original top surface remains undisturbed, and a parabolic surface profile is obtained. The flow process is well corroborated by the experiment observations (Bui et al., 2008) and other numerical simulations (Bui et al., 2008; Peng et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2021). Furthermore, the pressure field obtained using the LDD method is smooth and free of any numerical noise. This is very important as the failure of the granular material is dependent on pressure. Inaccurate pressure computations may give rise to low accuracy of simulations. For example, in SPH modeling of granular flows, additional stabilization and smoothing techniques such as artificial viscosity and shepherd filter should be used to ensure stable and reliable simulations (Chambon et al., 2011; Nguyen et al., 2017; Peng et al., 2019b). However, owing to the pressure-velocity formulation and the solution of PPE, the LDD method gives accurate pressure results without any additional treatments.

The comparisons of the final profiles from the LDD simulation and the experimental data are shown in Fig. 5, in which the numerical results from SPH (Bui et al., 2008) are also included. The three profiles agree well, indicating that the LDD method with the simple viscoplastic DP model satisfactorily captures the flow dynamics and produces correct final deposit shape.

In the viscoplastic DP model, there are two constitutive parameters, i.e., the friction angle ϕ and the regularization parameter m , of which m is a numerical parameter. To check the influence of m , four simulations with $m = 10, 100, 1000, 10,000 \text{ s}$ are carried out. The profiles of deposit from the four simulations are shown in Fig. 6. It shows that the simulations with $m \geq 100$ have identical profiles, which means that the parameter m does not have influence on the simulation results if it is larger than 100 s . On the other hand, the simulation with $m = 10 \text{ s}$ gives a flatter profile, showing that the material has unphysically large fluidity. This indicates that with $m = 10 \text{ s}$ the model cannot produce large enough viscosities for the quasi-static regions, hence a larger value of m should be used in the simulation. It is worthy noting that even with a very large m , the simulation is stable and the numerical efficiency is not affected by the large viscosities in the solid-like areas. The reason of this robustness is the utilization of the implicit velocity solver, which can handle large values of viscosity without difficulty. This feature is important, as large viscosities may severely reduce the numerical efficiency in methods with explicit treatment of the viscous effect (Zago et al., 2018). Through the numerical investigation of m , it is found that the values equal to or larger than 100 are sufficient. Consequently, in all the subsequent simulations, m is always taken as 100 s .

The convergence behavior of the LDD method is also investigated. Three simulations with varying point spacing, i.e., $\Delta r = 5, 2, \text{ and } 1 \text{ mm}$

Fig. 4. The simulated collapse process.

Fig. 5. Comparisons of the final profiles obtained from LDD simulations, the experiments, and SPH simulations from Bui et al. (2008).

Fig. 6. The influence of the regularization parameter m on the final deposition.

Fig. 7. The influence of point spacing Δr on the final deposition.

are conducted. The final profiles obtained from the three simulations are shown in Fig. 7. It is found that the simulation with $\Delta r = 5$ mm gives a shorter run-out and a slightly different profile, whereas the run-out and profiles from the other two simulations are almost identical. This observation indicates that once the point spacing is lower than a threshold, further refining the spatial resolution does not give rise to notable change in the simulation results. In other words, the LDD method for granular flow modeling has good convergence property.

4.1.2. Effect of the point regularization

The point regularization technique is crucial to the stability and accuracy of the simulation. To demonstrate this, a simulation without the PBD technique is performed. The collapse processes obtained from the simulations with and without PBD are shown in Fig. 8. It is found that without the PBD technique, the points follow closely the flow streamlines, quickly resulting in an anisotropic point distribution. This phenomenon is also observed in other numerical methods with second-

Fig. 8. The comparison of results obtained with and without the PBD point regularization.

order consistent field approximations, such as MPM (Solowski and Sloan, 2015) and the KGF-SPH method (Huang et al., 2019). This irregular point distribution leads to loss of volume conservation, unphysical simulations, and instabilities or even premature termination of computation. On the other hand, with the PBD technique, the LDD method gives rise to very regular point distributions, and stable and accurate simulations. Similar observation was also made when LDD is applied to free-surface water flows (Bašić et al., 2019; Bašić et al., 2020).

4.2. Interaction between granular flow and obstacle

As protection structures are commonly used to mitigate hazards caused by geophysical flows, e.g., fast landslides, snow avalanches, and debris flows, the investigation on interactions between granular flows and obstacles is of practical importance (Calvetti et al., 2017; Leonardi and Pirulli, 2020). The impact of granular flows on a rigid barrier was experimentally studied by Moriguchi et al. (2009). Because its simple geometry, clear loading condition, and detailed description of the test process and results, the test becomes a popular benchmark for numerical methods, and was later analyzed using different approaches, including the volume-of-fluid method (VOF) (Moriguchi et al., 2009) and SPH (He et al., 2018b; Neto and Borja, 2018; Zhan et al., 2019b). The previous numerical example in Section 4.1 demonstrates that the LDD method

well captures the flow dynamics of granular flows. In this section, we will check the performance of LDD in reproducing interaction forces between granular flows and obstacles.

The configuration of the test is shown in Fig. 9. A flume is setup with a slope angle of θ , in which a rigid barrier and a sand box are built. A load cell is installed behind the barrier, which measures the normal impact force exerted by the granular flow. A total 50 kg of sand is placed into the sand box. During the test, the gate of the sand box is opened quickly to let the sand flow down the flume. The sand flow first impacts on the barrier and then some material overtops the obstacle. The width of the flume is 0.3 m, the bulk density of the sand is 1379 kg/m³ (Moriguchi et al., 2009).

Following the test configuration, a 2D numerical model is created for the LDD simulations with a point spacing $\Delta r = 5$ mm. In the tests, the flume surface are processed by gluing the same sand material onto it. Therefore, a non-slip boundary condition can be assumed in the numerical simulations. As discussed in Moriguchi et al. (2009), it is difficult to determine the friction angle of the sand in the dynamic process from laboratory tests. Consequently, Moriguchi et al. (2009) and Neto and Borja (2018) employed numerical tests to calibrate the friction angle, and reported that $\phi = 35^\circ$ gives results in good agreement with the tests in terms of impact force. Therefore, in the first LDD simulation, the friction angle $\phi = 35^\circ$ is used with a slope inclination of $\theta = 45^\circ$. The impact force F on the rigid barrier is computed as

$$F = \sum_i^N p_i A_i \quad (27)$$

Fig. 9. The configuration of the test on granular flow impact on a rigid obstacle.

Fig. 10. Time histories of impact force with $\phi = 35^\circ$ and $\theta = 45^\circ$.

where N is the total number of boundary points on the barrier, p_i and A_i denote the pressure and area of the point, respectively. The area is computed as $A_i = B\Delta r$, where $B = 0.3$ m is the width of the flume.

4.2.1. Impact force and flow process

The time histories of the impact force obtained from the LDD simulation and the experiment are shown in Fig. 10. In the simulation, except PBD, the LDD method does not use any other stabilization or smoothing techniques, the shown time history of the impact force from LDD is without any averaging or smoothing. It can be observed that the numerical results are in good agreement with the experimental data. The simulation accurately models the arriving time of the flow front, as well as the accumulation of impact force on the barrier. This is an accuracy not achieved in previous simulations (Moriguchi et al., 2009; Neto and Borja, 2018; Zhan et al., 2019b). There are slight discrepancies between the numerical and experimental results in the later phase of the flow. Nevertheless, the differences are small and generally the LDD gives accurate results in terms of the impact force.

Fig. 11 shows the simulated flow process. As observed in the test, the sand quickly flows down the flume after the opening of the gate, arriving at the obstacle in around 0.78 s. After the initial impact, the material accumulates in front of the obstacle and finally overtops it. The whole flow process is in close agreement with the experiment and other simulations (Moriguchi et al., 2009; Neto and Borja, 2018; Zhan et al., 2019b). It should be noted that in Moriguchi et al. (2009), where the volume-of-fluid (VOF) method is employed to simulate the flow, it is reported that there is no overtopping of the material when $\phi = 35^\circ$ is used in their simulation. However, in the corresponding LDD simulation, some spillage is observed. This spillage is also observed in other simulations using Lagrangian point-based methods (Neto and Borja, 2018; Zhan et al., 2019b). This discrepancy might be attributed to the interface tracking in the VOF method, which induces numerical diffusion and additional damping that slow down the flow (Fringier et al., 2005; So et al., 2012).

4.2.2. Comparisons with VOF

Furthermore, the performance of LDD in modeling the impact force is compared with those of VOF and SPH. In Moriguchi et al. (2009), three simulations with $\phi = 30^\circ, 35^\circ$, and 40° are carried out with the same flume inclination $\theta = 45^\circ$. Following the same computational conditions, three LDD simulations are performed. Note that the LDD and VOF employ very similar constitutive model. They both use the viscoplastic DP model, but with different regularization methods. In this work, the

Fig. 12. Comparisons of histories of impact force from VOF (Moriguchi et al., 2009) and LDD.

regularization Eq. (6) is adopted, whereas in the VOF simulations, an upper limit of viscosity is directly used to prevent singularity (Moriguchi et al., 2009).

The results on the time history of the impact force are given in Fig. 12. Generally, the simulations from LDD and VOF with the same friction angle have the similar trend in the time history of impact force. With $\phi = 30^\circ$, a peak impact force can be obtained with both methods, whereas no obvious peak force is observed in the simulations with the rest two friction angles. It seems that the existence of peak value is dependent on the flow velocity. When the frictional angle is lower, the velocity of flow front is higher and the impact is more violent. Therefore, it generates larger impact force (Moriguchi et al., 2009; Li et al., 2020) and more obvious spillage. Consequently, a peak is observed from the time-force curve. On the other hand, in cases with high frictional angles, the velocity is lower. The material gradually accumulates behind the obstacle without violent impact and spillage; therefore, the time-force curves without peak are obtained. This observation will be further confirmed by numerical and experimental results with different inclinations, which will be discussed in Section 4.2.4.

The increase of impact force in the material accumulation stage is also similar in all the three groups of simulations. However, there are also major differences. First, the LDD method gives better results, which

Fig. 11. Snapshots of the granular flow with $\phi = 35^\circ$ and $\theta = 45^\circ$.

can be observed from the simulation with $\phi = 35^\circ$. The result from LDD is in close agreement with the experiment, while the result from VOF has larger discrepancy, especially in terms of the final impact force. Second, the LDD method captures better the arriving time of the flow front. It is found that in all the three groups of simulations, VOF predicts later arriving time. This observation is in agreement with our previous analysis that in VOF simulations the flows are unphysically slowed down because of the additional damping.

4.2.3. Comparisons with SPH

In [Neto and Borja \(2018\)](#), SPH is employed to model the granular flow impact with $\phi = 33^\circ, 35^\circ$, and 44° . The flume inclination remains to be $\theta = 45^\circ$. We performed three simulations using the LDD method with the same conditions. Note that different constitutive models are used in the LDD and SPH simulations. LDD uses the viscoplastic DP model, while an elastoplastic DP model is adopted in the SPH simulations. Additionally, the way to treat the shear stress-related term in the momentum equation is different.

The comparison on the results of impact force is shown in [Fig. 13](#). Generally, there are many differences between the results from the two methods. In the SPH simulations, the arriving time is independent of the friction angle. Furthermore, the impact force is overestimated with all the three friction angles. In the LDD simulations, the influence of friction angle is more obvious. First, the friction angle controls the arriving time: a larger friction angle always results in a later arriving time. Second, the shape of the time-force curves is dependent on friction angle. A peak force can be observed in the simulation with $\phi = 33^\circ$, whereas in the simulations with larger friction angles, the impact force does not have a peak value. It increases steadily and eventually reaches a stable value. Third, with a large friction angle ($\phi > 40^\circ$), the final impact force can be relatively small. This is also confirmed by the VOF-based simulations ([Moriguchi et al., 2009](#)). In the simulation with $\phi = 44^\circ$, the friction angle is only slightly smaller than the slope angle. It is natural that the flow is slow and the impact force is small.

Based on the comparison with the experimental data in the case with $\phi = 35^\circ$, we may have the preliminary conclusion that LDD with the viscoplastic DP model gives more reasonable results. This may be mainly attributed to the difference in constitutive model. SPH employs an elastoplastic model with history-dependent stress tensor, whereas LDD uses a viscoplastic model and considers the influence of shear stress using the Laplacian term. Although they both use the DP yield criterion, the different treatments of the stress tensor may induce huge differences in the simulation results. Indeed, this can be confirmed by looking back at the results from VOF. Because LDD and VOF employ the same

constitutive model and the same treatment of the shear stress-related term, the agreement between LDD and VOF results is better than that between LDD and SPH. Moreover, the smooth pressure and velocity fields obtained from the two implicit solvers undoubtedly help in achieving better impact forces, and avoid the numerical noise observed in SPH simulations ([Peng et al., 2016](#); [Nguyen et al., 2017](#); [Szewc, 2017](#)).

4.2.4. Influence of the flume inclination

The influence of the flume inclination is further investigated. Five simulations with flume inclinations $\theta = 45^\circ, 50^\circ, 55^\circ, 60^\circ$ and 65° are conducted with a fixed friction angle $\phi = 35^\circ$. As shown in [Fig. 14](#), the obtained time histories of impact force are compared with those from the laboratory tests ([Moriguchi et al., 2009](#)). It is observed that the LDD simulations successfully capture all important features of the evolution of impact force. The results are in close agreement with the data from the tests. The influence of the flume inclination is correctly modelled: a larger inclination gives rise to a shorter arriving time, a higher peak of impact force, and a larger slope of the time-force curve. It also reproduces the phenomenon that peak forces only present in cases with larger inclination, and with the increase of the inclination, the peak forces and the post-peak decrease of the impact force become more obvious.

We further analyze the results quantitatively with four indices, i.e., the peak force, the final force, the arriving time, and the time when the peak force is measured. These four indices are selected because they are important for the risk assessment of granular flow-like natural hazards such as fast landslides and rock/snow avalanches. The change of these indices with the inclinations is given in [Fig. 15](#) together with those obtained from the tests. Note that in the case with $\theta = 45^\circ$, there is no peak impact force. Furthermore, the relative error is also computed as

$$e = \frac{|I_{EXP} - I_{LDD}|}{I_{EXP}} \times 100\% \quad (28)$$

where I_{EXP} and I_{LDD} denote the values of the index obtained from the experiments and the LDD simulations, respectively. It can be seen that LDD gives highly accurate results in terms of the peak impact force and the arriving time. For the peak impact force, the relative errors in all the cases are less than 6%. For the arriving time, the relative errors are less than 3% except for the case with $\theta = 65^\circ$, where the error is 9%. For the final impact force and the time when the peak force is measured, the errors are larger; nevertheless, most of the errors are less than 10%, with three cases having errors larger than 10%. We also observe faster decreases of impact force in the cases with high inclination, e.g. $\theta = 60^\circ$ and 65° . The discrepancies may be attributed to that the viscoplastic DP model cannot fully capture the material behavior, especially the change of frictional angle in the dense flow regime ([Jop et al., 2006](#)). Another possible reason for the lower final impact force is that in the present treatment, the behavior of granular material at rest is undefined. The regularized viscoplastic model uses very high viscosity values to mimic the solid behavior, which does not allow a true static state. This may lead to excessive spillage and lower final impact force.

5. Conclusions

In this work, a Lagrangian differencing dynamics (LDD) method is employed to model granular flows, in which the granular media are modelled as continuum, i.e., as an incompressible viscoplastic material with the Drucker-Prager yield criterion. The LDD method is a truly meshless and Lagrangian method based on the second-order consistent approximations of the gradient and Laplacian operators. Smooth and second-order accurate pressure and velocity fields are obtained by solving the generalized Navier-Stokes equations in a pressure-velocity decoupled fashion. Furthermore, the introduced implicit velocity solver can handle large viscosities from the constitutive model. The position-based dynamics technique is used to ensure regular point

Fig. 13. Comparisons of histories of impact force from SPH ([Neto and Borja, 2018](#)) and LDD.

Fig. 14. The time histories of impact force in cases with varying inclination.

Fig. 15. Quantitative comparisons between LDD and experimental results: (a) peak impact force, (b) final impact force, (c) arriving time, (d) time for peak force.

distribution, which further improves the accuracy and stability of the method.

The performance of the presented LDD method is demonstrated through two numerical examples, i.e., the collapse of a granular column and the impact of granular flows on a rigid barrier. It is found that the method provides results in close quantitative agreement with the experimental data. The LDD method not only reproduces the flow dynamics correctly, more importantly, it also models the arriving time and the peak impact force with high accuracy.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Chong Peng: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing - original draft. **Martina Bašić:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing - review & editing. **Branko Blagojević:** Supervision, Writing - review & editing. **Josip Bašić:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing - review & editing. **Wei Wu:** Supervision, Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

The authors would like to thank the funding from the National Natural Science Foundation of China (51709230). The work in this paper is also partly funded by the EU Horizon 2020 RISE projects HERCULES (778360) and FRAMED (734485), and the Nazarbayev University Research Fund (SOE2017001).

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